

SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Azizov Abbos Obidovich, AKFA University,
ESL Professor, Department “School of Education”

In today’s highly competitive world, we all know that the role and importance of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship in the implementation of social and economic policy has been increasing gradually in Uzbekistan. This is because the development of this sector from the first days of Uzbekistan’s independence has been a crucial driving force in addressing the most acute of the crisis issues that were left to us from the planning and distributive system.

The advanced development of this sector trace on the global financial and economic downturn in 2008. At that time the model of reforms and modernization, which our Republic had chosen, played a great important role in preventing and neutralizing the negative and destructive impact of the global financial and economic crisis.

In a word, the Republic of Uzbekistan tried to overcome the negative effects of the crisis as well as just did it. In that way, our government paid attention to enquire the wealth of experience gained over the centuries in the advanced and developing nations.

It is admitted that there are many reasons and factors to prioritize advanced development of small business and entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

First of all, as the international practice shows, small business, as a critical structure-shaping sector of economy, serves as a principal source of filling the domestic market with essential goods and services. Small business does not only populate certain niches in the economy, but it is also instrumental in the economy’s diversification and ensuring its sustainable growth rates. It is hard to overestimate, especially in our conditions, the vital role of the entrepreneurial business in providing for employment and growth in people’s incomes. During the period between 2011 and 2015, many new jobs were created in the economy of our country, whereby over 60 percent of them accounted for small business and private entrepreneurship. These indicators are rather telling in their own right, and, in my opinion, so are they for any other country. As a result, this sphere currently covers more than 75 percent of the total employed population.

Second, compact in form, agile and efficient in decision making, receptive to innovation, small business is more flexible and swift in adapting quickly to changes in the demand and the situation in the global and regional markets, and in timely addressing its challenges.

Third, starting and running small business does not require large expenses and capital investments, which allows for faster and easier modernization, technical and

technological re-equipment of production facilities, introduce new types of goods, constantly upgrade its range and provide for competitive edge.

Fourth, the higher sustainability of this sphere, compared to large enterprises, for the challenges and consequences of the global financial and economic crisis. Only through an accelerated promotion and a predominant status of small business and private entrepreneurship have we been able to cope with the negative impact of the 2008-2009 slowdown with lesser pain and loss, and reorient – within a brief span of time – the production capacities with an eye to the changing global market conditions. In manufacturing industry, the growth rates of small businesses and private entrepreneurship during 2008-2009 averaged 23-24 percent, while services expanded at least 15-16 percent.

Fifth, small business is not only a source of income, but also a tool for discovering the creative and intellectual abilities of people. This area allows everyone to show their individual talents and capabilities, thus forming a new layer of people – the enterprising, initiative-prone, inclined to independent activity, and able to achieve their goals.

Moreover, there are tactic principles and foundations the development of entrepreneurship and small business is based in Uzbekistan. This has been reason to a powerful legislative and normative framework, its constant improvement, the system of government assistance in the provision of business with incentives and preferences and modernization. The fundamentally important in the development of private enterprise has been the 2000 law on guarantees of the freedom of entrepreneurship, which fixes all the basic guarantees and conditions for the free participation of citizens in enterprising business, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of economic entities and business. In tax and taxation policy, in the period from 2005 to 2012, the single tax payment for micro and small enterprises has been reduced more than 2.5 times from 13 to 5 percent of the turnover, while folk craftsmanship and family business is not taxed at all or taxed at minimum rates.

It is difficult to overestimate the role of the state in the formation and establishment of small business and entrepreneurship, given its decisive contribution to the development of industrial, social, communication and transport infrastructure. For example, suffice it to mention the successful experience of operating high-tech business in the Navoi Free Industrial and Economic Zone and the Angren Special Industrial Zone have been created. The decision has been made in Uzbekistan envisions that in these areas that are being created as free zones – zones of preferences – all the infrastructure for those enterprises, foreign investment into which exceeds 30 million dollars, is 100 percent funded by the state.

At the legislative level, it has been introduced the principle of the priority of entrepreneur rights in the relations of businesses with government, law enforcement

and regulatory agencies. An order is in force that prohibits planned tax audits of small businesses within three years from the date of registration and limiting subsequent conduction of tax audits in steadily working and honest taxpayers.

Over the last six years, the gross domestic product has been growing at an annual rate of at least 8.2 percent. Compared to the year 2000, the GDP has enlarged 2.9 times, the industrial production increased 2.6 times, the volume of investments in the economy multiplied 3.4 times, while foreign direct investment has expanded more than 20 times.

Overall, all of the performance provide for a rapid economic growth and advancement of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.